

Impact of Leadership Styles on Quality Work Culture in Ngo's Of Pakistan

Author's Details:

- (1)**Sohail Anwar** - The Superior College Lahore
(2)**Umair Tufail** - University of Sargodha
(3)**Asif Nazir** - The Superior College Lahore
(4)**Muhammad Muzaffar** - The University of Lahore
(5)**Muhammad Waheed** - The Superior College Lahore

Abstract

Leadership styles have enormous impact on the performance of employees and achievement of organizational goals. Some organizations never encourage quality work culture while others consider quality work to serve the clients as a yardstick to measure the performance of the employees. Moreover, the culture that promotes quality ultimately leads to workplace harmonization. Numerous studies have reviewed different concepts pertaining to quality work culture, leadership, leadership theories, and leadership styles; so, the current research study has significant theoretical background.

This study was conducted on 14 different NGOs (Non-Government Organizations) across Pakistan. These organizations are also called as humanitarian organizations or not-for-profit sector. The targeted population for the study was fulltime employees working for operations and other supporting departments in the humanitarian organizations, who are dealing with management issues and researches of the similar kind. The data were collected from 150 respondents working in different NGOs in Pakistan through questionnaires. Most of the respondents were either managers or deputy managers.

The core purpose of this study was to explore whether a significant relationship exists between the leadership styles such as transactional and transformational leadership styles and quality-focused work culture or not. This study revealed that significant relationship exists between the two mentioned leadership styles and the quality work culture. Our finding reveals that transformational leadership has more significant effects on quality work culture in comparison of transactional leadership style. This study has been conducted with a hope to improve the work culture in the NGOs of Pakistan by finding out the most significant leadership style.

Key words: Leadership styles, Quality Work Culture, NGO

Introduction

This study examines leadership styles and their impact on quality work culture in the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in Pakistan.

For a long time, leadership has been a focus of different discussions and different leadership styles, which received different feedbacks from followers in different societies and cultures. This study reveals the positive paradigm, which provided impartially-reported reality about the significance of different styles of leadership for creating quality work culture in the organizations. In this descriptive research, the aim has been to determine the outline of parameters, which can envisage the underlying phenomena. As a part of the descriptive research methodology, data collection is based on fair practices and ordered reasoning. In order to analyze the hypothesized relationships, quantitative research method has been used.

During the last several years, the organizational management literature is focused on work culture as a very significant indicator behind the organizational success of the firms engaged in business. Organizations are adapting various techniques for improving their work cultures. Some organizations almost never focused on quality work culture as a priority; however, a significant number of organizations consider quality work culture as vital for better service delivery to their customers. Moreover, workplace harmonization is assured when an organization has quality work culture (Ali et. al., 2015).

Most of today's top performing organizations are run by top managers and industry leaders, who pay special attention to the employees' behaviors and performances. As a rule, good leaders demand of their employees to proactively and dynamically engage themselves for performing their tasks. In the nutshell, leadership styles influence the quality of organizational work culture. In case, the leaders exhibit poor leadership qualities or inappropriate styles, it can negatively impact the work culture of an organization (Haq and Kuchinke, 2016).

Literature Review

Many researchers have reviewed different concepts of leadership such as leadership styles and their impact on the quality-driven work culture, so the current research study is one of the efforts in this established research area. The investigation of the available literature facilitated us to recognize the gap, which exists in the literature, and it has provided the basis for the current research.

Leadership

The scholars, as a rule, describe initiatives according to their individual points of view while the acceptance of their descriptions brings enthusiasm to their concepts. After thorough assessment of the leadership literature, it has been observed that the number of leadership meanings are approximately same as the people who have endeavored to characterize the idea (Stogdill, 1974).

Leadership is collaboration between individuals who belong to a group. Leaders act as mediators of change, and they are people whose demonstrations influence other individuals more than other individuals' demonstrations influence them (Bass, 1985).

The new leadership concept depends on empowering individuals to work skillfully and co-operatively inside and beyond the limits of the organization. Leaders must inculcate vitality and dedication among individuals through making rousing inquiries or sharing a ground-breaking vision (Gratton, 2007).

Power is fundamental to leaders since it is a compelling method to affect supporters. Without control, there is no leadership. To be fruitful, leaders must be in control and the followers must respect their positions. Leaders must impact their followers, peers, and other stakeholders (McClelland, 1985).

Leaders with high vitality endeavor to accomplish the defined objectives. Leaders with high vitality additionally have a tendency to have stamina to endure pressure. Leaders having high vitality are normally excited and don't disappoint those, who trust them. In any case, they are not seen as pushy and unpalatable. They have a tendency to have high resilience to dissatisfaction, since they have to make arrangements to get very tough tasks done (Bass, 1990).

Charismatic leaders inculcate exclusive respect among their follower by valuing good performances and expressing trust in their followers. Leaders, who show high performance, can inspire their followers by setting higher execution objectives and make them achieve those objectives. Such performance is not possible unless their followers perceive those objectives as achievable and sensible. If the followers need trust in their capacities to meet the leader's exclusive requirements, they may oppose the leader's actions to influence them. The assertion of certainty and convictions by the leaders are then questioned. Charismatic leadership is most probably found in the organizations, which are attempting to survive, or in well-established organizations; however, it is more effective in well-established organizations (House, 1977).

Mostly, the theories of charismatic and transformational leadership need adequate determination of basic influence of processes. The self-concept theory of charismatic leadership gives detailed clarification of a leaders' influences on their followers, however, even more explanations are needed for this theory in terms of how the different types of influencing processes collaborate, their relative significance, and whether they are effective (Bryman, 1993; Beyer, 1999; Yukl, 1999).

Even though most of the contemporary theorists have abstained from giving meaning to leadership, Kellerman visualized leadership as a symmetrical triangle, in which, the three sides are the leaders, the followers, and the context (Volckmann, 2012). She perceives that the leaders are significant because they are behind the historic situation of this world that improved for people over many centuries; however, she believes that the followers are as essential as the leaders, which Bass (1990) also mentioned, and most strangely, she considered the setting as an equally critical factor behind the leadership processes.

The literature review confirms that the leadership concept has evolved over time, and after considering it as an individual quality, it is currently comprehended, at least by a few researchers, that leadership is more than a single attribute since it is a complex phenomenon, in which, the followers and the context have critical roles to play.

Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is different what it has been perceived by many contemporary and past theorists because it is based on the great role that a transformational leader plays in association with his/her followers or exercises authority to perform actions, which result in certain predominant social and organizational profits. The transformational leaders promote the inspiration and profound quality of their followers (House & Shamir, 1993). Transformational leaders lead the associations while their followers use their qualities to perform regular tasks, and inspire others with their convictions to achieve their objectives. This affects the execution of important tasks in order to fulfill a certain objective. According to Bass, every transformational leader "endeavors to instigate followers to reshuffle their needs by rising above self-interests and fulfills the commonly requested needs." This theory accommodates Maslow's (1954) higher needs theory. Transformational leadership is a way of action that focuses on qualities, convictions and dispositions that increase a leader's abilities to lead the change process.

The literature recommends that the leaders and their followers should put aside individual interests for the benefit of the whole group. The leader is then requested to focus on followers' needs and contributions to the change process (House and Aditya, 1997). If we focus on established leadership theories, they show that the moral degree of initiative further separates transformational leadership from other forms of leadership. The transformational leaders have the ability to identify the prerequisites of change, pick up the assertion, delegate responsibilities to others, inspire followers with change can do for the group and bring about the change (Bums, 2003). This kind of leaders treats juniors independently and seeks after to build up their ethics, cognizance and abilities by having attention on their work. These leaders persuade people with empowered vision. They are "visionary leaders" who understand the natures of their followers and push them to perform towards higher and more inclusive needs and purposes (Bums, 2003).

Transactional Leadership

The leadership theories, which were presented during the late 1970s and mid-1980s, diverted from previous viewpoints about the leaders, leadership perspective and the nature of relationship between the supporters and leaders. Transactional leadership has been depicted as a leader-follower affiliation, which is based on progression of assertions among the followers and their leader (House & Shamir, 1993). The transactional leadership theory "depends on correspondence, through which, leaders influence followers and accept the influence of their followers as well." Multiple analyses uncovered that transactional leaders demonstrate inconsistent level of activity but they have strong idea of relations with their followers.

According to (Bass & Avolio, 1994), transactional leadership "is a kind of unexpected reward initiative that has dynamic and positive level of confidence among the leaders and followers because the followers agreed to achieve the mutually agreed targets." From the leaders' perspectives, these prizes may include appreciation, rewards and credit for work accomplishment. For good work, positive help should be given, the pay should justify the achievements, and participation should be encouraged. The leader could rather focus on errors, and maintain a strategic distance from the reactions and delays to make decisions. This disposition is articulated as

"management by-exemption" and it can be executed by dynamic or inactive or exchanges. The distinction between these two kinds of exchanges is presented based on the planning of the leaders' contribution. In the dynamic shape, the leader persistently screens execution and proactively intercedes (Avolio & Bass, 1997).

Quality Work Culture

This term has been thoroughly analyzed in several perspectives of social sciences, humanities, business and history. Here, we are concerned with just a single type of culture, which is work culture or organizational culture. It comprises of common convictions, values, traits, and practices, because of which, the members of an organization work together. The culture is a vast thing in its scope because it defines how the employees behave, show their skills, comprehend the organization, and develop association with their organization. In the nutshell, culture is summation of choices, activities, and performance of people in an organization (Rogel, 2014).

Employees need quality work culture because it incorporates rewards, fulfillment of needs, common values and professional practices. Quality work culture assures sense of purpose, mutual respect, and sense of duty while permitting decent variety in thought and activity. This definition assumes that quality work culture reflects in the practices and standards of an organization, which emerges through common attributes and essential suppositions of the people, who work for an organization. In order to remain valuable and survive in the market place, creating a supportive work atmosphere is imperative for all the organizations. The literature shows that decent behavior towards employees ultimately results in improving the overall performance of an organization (Robert and Thomas, 2007).

Additionally, the blend of characteristics of an organization and its employees emerges from what is by and large viewed as proper approaches to thought and action. Various key estimations are available, which analyze the organizational work culture. The organizational culture is analyzed through key estimations, which are observed in the large portion of the organizations, for example, responsibility, versatility, coordinated effort, duty, effective correspondence, strengthening values, adaptability, confidence, standard methodologies, trust, ceaseless change, and mutual respect. If the mentioned key qualities are assured to a sufficient level, the operations of an organization will be smooth with few errors (Robert and Thomas, 2007). In addition, quality work culture is based on four particular factors, which include leaders' activities and practices, what they focus on, how they allocate resources, what are their reward and punishment principles, and what is their vision of the organization's future (Pellet, 2013).

Even with extreme rivalry, it is possible to find quality work culture at various organizational levels. Specialists regularly examine corporate/organizational culture to further their knowledge about the organization. Organizations can't build up an organizational culture that significantly differs from the predominant social/national culture where it operates (Lagrosen, 2002). Blake and Mouton (1989) mentioned some rules, through which, organizations can expand their viability and relevance to the marketplace. They additionally pointed out that for staying viable, the organizational targets must be solid and clear to every member of the organization, and the organization should have quality work culture that backs effective employees, promotes inclusiveness through collaboration, provides specialized trainings to employees and possesses effective leadership. A powerful organization almost always has quality work culture that supports employees. When the targets, vision and mission are clear, it leads the organization towards substantial accomplishments.

Methodology

This study was conducted on different NGOs/humanitarian organizations operating in Pakistan. The targeted population for the study comprises fulltime employees from operations and other supporting departments, who are dealing with managerial affairs and researches of similar kinds. The size of the population is 150. The research instrument utilized for gathering essential information was questionnaire, which is the most popular data collection technique in the world of research. The questions asked for data collection were close-ended. Surveys help accumulating data that shows mentalities, assessments, practices, actualities, and other useful data

forms. A questionnaire with three parts was used for different variables of the research: Part-A: Demographic Details, Part-B: Leadership Styles (Transformational and Transactional Leadership) and Part-C: Quality Work Culture. The work culture was assessed by using the self-assessment checklist based on the assumption: "Be the manager you would love to have, managing a healthy workplace." 14 questions were asked to assess the quality work culture in NGOs (Ali et. al., 2015). Multi-factor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ Form 5X) was used for assessments pertaining to leadership style (Bass and Avolio, 1995). The data was obtained from questionnaire, which was entered and coded in SPSS 24 statistical software. The analysis of descriptive statistics was performed in SPSS to perform calculations such as frequency, mean, variance, KMO, correlation, regression, and Bartlett's test. Reliability was tested through Cronbach's alpha.

Research Findings and Results:

The questionnaire had 35 questions, 5 questions pertaining to demographics, 16 questions regarding leadership styles and 14 questions about quality work culture. Large number of questionnaires was distributed and 150 responses were received.

Characteristics of Respondents:

Since the respondents belong to different areas and different organizations; so, the questionnaire used for the study has 5 identified areas, which show the basic characteristics of respondents.

Table-1: Demographic Details

		Frequency	Percent			Frequency	Percent	
Length of Service	Above 15 years	5	3.3	Education	PhD	1	0.7	
	10 to 15 years	8	5.3		M.Phil/M.S	23	15.3	
	5 to 9 years	20	13.3		Master's	68	45.3	
	2 to 4 years	58	38.7		Bachelor's	52	34.7	
	Less than 2 years	59	39.3		Professional Degrees	6	4.0	
	Total	150	100.0		Total	150	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent			Frequency	Percent	
Age	Above 45 years	7	4.7	Designation	General Manager	10	6.7	
	35 to 45 years	18	12.0		Senior Manager	13	8.7	
	25 to 34 years	89	59.3		Manager	37	24.7	
	Less than 25 years	36	24.0		Deputy Manager	56	37.3	
	Total	150	100.0		Officer	34	22.7	
		Frequency	Percent				Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	119	79.3			Total	150	100.0
	Female	31	20.7					
	Total	150	100.0					

The table shows that 5 respondents served for more than 15 years, which is 3.3%, 8 respondents served from 10 to 15 years, which is 5.3%, 20 respondents served from 5 to 9 years, which is 13.3%, 58 respondents served from 2 to 4 years, which is 38.7%, and 59 respondents served for less than 2 years, which is 39.3% of the respondents. Hence, most of the respondents were new workers.

It was found that 7 respondents were more than 45 years old, which is 4.7%, 18 respondents were from 35 to 45 years old, which is 12%, 89 respondents were 25 to 34 years old, which is 59.3%, and 36 respondents were younger than 25 years, which is 24%. Hence, most of the respondents were in the bracket of 25-34 years.

While analyzing education, we found that 1 respondent (0.7%) had a Ph.D. degree, 23 respondents (15.3%) had M.Phil/M.S. degrees, 68 respondents (45.3%) were master’s degree holders, 52 respondents (34.7%) had bachelor’s degrees, and 6 respondents (4%) had professional degrees.

As far as their designations are concerned, 10 respondents (6.7%) were general managers, 13 respondents (8.7%) were senior managers, 37 respondents (24.7%) were managers, 56 respondents (37.3%) were deputy managers and 34 respondents (22.7%) were officers. Thus, most of the respondents were deputy managers.

In the gender section, we found that 119 respondents (79.3%) were men while 31 respondents (20.7%) were women; therefore, men were remarkably more than women.

Descriptive Summary:

The data has been collected through questionnaires, which was later transformed into the SPSS framework for analysis. Descriptive analysis was conducted on SPSS 24. This analysis tells us about the three variables: Transactional Leadership Style, Transformational Leadership Style and Quality Work Culture. This study is based on the responses of 150 participants. The minimum and maximum limits of these items vary between 1 to 5 points on the Likert Scale. The mean scores range from 3.808 to 4.134. The standard deviations range from 0.588 to 0.645. The variance value ranges between 0.346 and 0.416.

Table-2: Descriptive Summary

Descriptive Statistics						
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Transactional	150	1.29	4.86	3.830	0.588	0.346
Transformational	150	1.71	5.00	3.808	0.609	0.371
Quality Work Culture	150	1.07	5.00	4.134	0.645	0.416

KMO and Bartlett’s Tests:

Table-3: KMO test for sampling adequacy and Bartlett’s Test for sphericity

	Items	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy. [KMO]	Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity		
			Approx. Chi-Square	df	Significance
Transactional Leadership	8	0.756	173.2	28	0
Transformational Leadership	8	0.701	208.7	28	0
Quality Work Culture	14	0.906	1014.2	91	0

The KMO test informs about the stability of the data and this value lies between 0 and 1. More than 0.5 is acceptable, more than 0.6 is reasonable, the values between 0.7 and 0.8 are too good and the value which is closer to 1 is excellent. In Table 3, all the values are good as the highest value is Quality Work Culture [KMO: 0.906], which is nearest to 1. The other values were also found: Transactional Leadership Style [KMO: 0.756] and Transformational Leadership Style [KMO: 0.701]. All the values are in good range; therefore, the data is valid.

Bartlett’s test is used to analyze significance of relationships between the variables. If the relation does not exist, there will be no further analysis. The significance value is below 0.05; so that table shows that all the values meet the conditions and this data is ready for further proceedings.

Cronbach’s Alpha test for reliability analysis:

Table-4: Cronbach's alpha test shows reliability of leadership styles and quality work culture

	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha based on standardized items	N of items
Transactional	0.697	0.709	7
Transformational	0.698	0.705	7
Quality Work Culture	0.908	0.910	14

The table given above shows the coefficient of Cronbach's alpha values obtained for transactional and transformational leadership styles and the quality of work culture. The value of the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.697 for transactional leadership, 0.698 for transformational leadership and 0.908 for quality work culture. Based on reliability test results of these three variables (including a dependent and two independent variables), the test results are acceptable based on the obtained Cronbach's alpha values. When the test value is above 0.5, it is acceptable and as the values increase, they become good, very good and finally, they are excellent when they are closer to 1. The results show that the coefficient of Cronbach's alpha for quality work culture is 0.908, which is excellent and the value for transformational leadership is 0.698 whereas for transactional leadership, it is 0.697. The internal consistency and reliability of used variables is good to proceed further. Previously, Cronbach's alpha value for quality work culture was measured as equal to 0.84 (Ali et. al., 2015).

Correlation Analysis

Table-5: Correlation between leadership styles and quality work culture

Correlations				
		Transactional	Transformational	Quality Work Culture
Transactional	Pearson Correlation	1	.653**	.601**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000
	N	150	150	150
Transformational	Pearson Correlation	.653**	1	.633**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000
	N	150	150	150
Quality Work Culture	Pearson Correlation	.601**	.633**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	
	N	150	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table-5 shows the correlations between dependent variables and independent variables, and the significance levels of correlations. Results show that both transactional and transformational leadership styles have positive correlation with the quality work culture but transformational leadership is more significantly correlated with quality work culture since the value of the correlation coefficient is 0.633. Transactional leadership has positive correlation with quality work culture, and the value of the correlation coefficient is 0.601, which shows that transformational leadership has higher effect on quality work culture because of higher correlation coefficient value (Ali et. al., 2015).

Regression Analysis:

Table-6: Regression Analysis

Adjusted R Square		0.455
Standardized Coefficients Beta	Transactional Leadership	0.326
	Transformational Leadership	0.420

Table 6 shows regression analysis between the quality work culture, and the leadership styles. The results revealed $\beta=0.326$ for transactional leadership while $\beta=0.420$ for transformational leadership, which means that they have significant relationship with quality work culture. It shows that transformational leadership has more impact on quality work culture. Previously, the adjusted R square value was 0.645 (Ali et. al., 2015).

Discussion and Conclusions:

This research has been conducted with a purpose to investigate whether any significant relation exists between style of leadership and quality work culture or not. The conclusions of the research are framed on the basis of the results obtained from the survey.

The research focused on two variables i.e. quality work culture and leadership styles. These variables were hypothesized and the relationship between them was investigated. Two leadership styles have been investigated, which create impact by creating quality-centric organizational culture. The research has been confined to non-governmental organizations (NGOs) operating in Pakistan.

The survey results, which were obtained through questionnaires, revealed that transactional and transformational leadership styles have positive correlations with quality work culture, but transformational leadership is more significantly correlated with quality work culture. On the other hand, transactional leadership also showed positive correlation with quality work culture.

Similarly, regression analysis confirms the findings of the correlation analyses by proving that both transactional and transformational leadership styles have significant relation with quality work culture; however, findings show that transformational leadership has more impact on quality work culture as compared to the transactional leadership.

References:

- i. Ali, N., Jangga, R., Ismail, M., Kamal, S. and Ali, M. (2015). *Influence of Leadership Styles in Creating Quality Work Culture. Procedia Economics and Finance*, 31, pp.161-169.
- ii. Asrar-ul-Haq, M. and Kuchinke, K. (2016). *Impact of leadership styles on employees' attitude towards their leader and performance: Empirical evidence from Pakistani banks. Future Business Journal*, 2(1), pp.54-64.
- iii. Bass, B.M. (1985). *Leadership and Performance beyond Expectations*. Publisher: Free Press, New York. (pp. 16)
- iv. Bass, B.M. (1990). *Bass & Stogdill's handbook of leadership (3rd Ed.)*. New York: Free Press.
- v. Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (1994). *Improving organizational effectiveness through transformational leadership*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- vi. Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (1997) *Full range leadership development: manual for the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire*, Mindgarden, Palo Alto, Calif.
- vii. Blake, R. R. & Mouton, J. S., 1989. *Grid Organization Development In W. E. Natemayer & J. T. McMahan, Classics of Organizational Behavior*, Prospect Heights, Illinois: Waveland Press, 3rd Edition
- viii. Bryman, A. (1993). *Charisma and leadership in organizations*. London: Sage.
- ix. Charles Rogel., 2014. *The 12th Attributes of a Strong Organizational Culture*, 18th March 2014, retrieved from <http://www.eremedia.com/tlnt/the-12-attributes-of-a-strong-organizational-culture/>

- x. Garton, S., & Richards, K. (2007). *Is distance education for teacher education second best?* *Teacher Trainer*, 21(3), 5-8.
- xi. House, R. J. (1977). *A 1976 theory of charismatic leadership*. In J. G. Hunt & L. L. Larson (Eds.), *Leadership: The cutting edge* (pp. 189–207). Carbondale: Southern Illinois University Press.
- xii. House, R. J., & Shamir, B. (1993). *Toward the integration of transformational, charismatic, and visionary theories*. M. M. Chemers, & R. Ayman (Eds.), *Leadership theory and research: Perspectives and direction*, 81–107.
- xiii. House, R., & Aditya, R. (1997). *The social scientific study of leadership: Quo Vadis?* *Journal of Management*, 23, 409-474.
- xiv. Lizz Pellet., 2013. *How Leaders Can Impact Organizational Cultures with Their Actions And Behavior*, 21 May 2013, retrieved from <http://www.halogensoftware.com/blog/how-leaders-can-impact-organizational-cultures-with-their-actions-and-behaviors>
- xv. Maslow, A. H. (1954). *Motivation and personality*. New York: Harper and Row.
- xvi. McClelland, D. C. (1985). *How motives, skills, and values determine what people do*. *American Psychologist*, 40(7), 812-825.
- xvii. McGregor, D. M. (2003). *The human side of enterprise*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- xviii. Stefan Lagrosen, 2002. *Exploring The Impact of Culture On Quality Management*, *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 20 (4), 473-487
- xix. Stogdill, R. (1974). *Handbook of leadership: A survey of theory and research*. Publisher: Free Press, New York. (pp. 259)
- xx. Volckmann, R. (2012). *“Fresh perspective: Barbara Kellerman and the leadership industry”*. *Articles from Integral Leadership Review*. 2012-06-08.
- xxi. Yukl, G. (1999). *An evaluation of conceptual weaknesses in transformational and charismatic leadership potential*. *Leadership Quarterly*, 10, 285–305.